

README.TXT

Title: Factors affecting foreign language anxiety among pre-service teachers of English

Description: This dataset contains responses to the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) (Horwitz et al., 1986), together with six background questions including English proficiency, degree programme, degree stage, subject nature and gender, to analyse Foreign Language Anxiety (FLA) among pre-service teachers of English.

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Materials:

1. All statistical analysis.doc
2. Data analysis.omv
3. Statistical analysis.omv

Software:

Jamovi used for statistical analysis (.omv): <https://www.jamovi.org/>